

Log Clustering for Increased Log Analysis Efficiency: Unsupervised Machine Learning for Failed Test Run Grouping in Broadcast Equipment Testing

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Abstract

Automated testing of broadcast systems generates large volumes of test logs containing failure reports that require manual analysis. When multiple tests fail due to common root causes, redundant investigation by different engineers wastes time and resources. This paper evaluates unsupervised machine learning techniques—specifically KMeans and HDBSCAN clustering algorithms—for automatically grouping failed test runs in the MediorNet product line at RIEDEL Communications Austria. The system processes semi-structured HTML test log files to extract composite feature vectors combining log text, test descriptions, headings, and metadata. We systematically evaluate the impact of text extraction strategies (extracting first error only versus all), feature vectorization approaches (BERT embeddings, TF-IDF, and hybrid representations) and component weighting schemes on clustering algorithm, namely KMeans and HDBSCAN, performance. Evaluation on $\approx 10,000$ failed test runs across 113 labeled test campaigns demonstrates that feature vectorization strategy is the primary determinant of vector quality, with TF-IDF achieving higher group separation and BERT providing better cohesion. Both KMeans and HDBSCAN achieve comparable external validation scores (ARI: 0.60 ± 0.22 vs. 0.57 ± 0.21), though HDBSCAN exhibits better alignment between internal and external metrics, as well as better suitability to expected single-member cluster scenarios, making it preferable for production deployment. Golden sample evaluation confirms practical feasibility the presented approach, demonstrating maturity for industrial deployment in broadcast equipment testing workflows.

Keywords: clustering, machine learning, natural language processing, unsupervised learning, log analysis, test automation, failure grouping

1 Introduction

Testing complex distributed systems such as MediorNet broadcasting equipment (RIEDEL Communications, 2025) at RIEDEL Communications generates large volumes of diagnostic logs from automated test procedures. The test suite in place contains over 1,000 test procedures across multiple test systems, with total runtime spanning two weeks. Each test execution generates text-based HTML log files. Failed test runs currently undergo manual triage partitioned by test system, with log contents unknown prior to inspection. Since failures frequently share common

underlying causes across test systems, this process carries inherent risk of redundant analysis wherein multiple engineers investigate identical issues, leading to inefficient resource utilization.

Traditional keyword-based log grouping approaches prove insufficient at scale, yielding high false positive rates (Lin et al., 2016). This motivates exploration of more sophisticated automated clustering techniques that can pre-group similar failures to reduce duplicate analysis effort. Prior work has demonstrated the applicability of clustering to log analysis in various domains. Egersdoerfer et al. derived features from logs via pretrained semantic embedding models and applied DBSCAN clustering (Egersdoerfer et al., 2023). Lin et al. utilized Hierarchical Agglomerative Clustering combined with knowledge bases for problem identification in online services (Lin et al., 2016). NetML jointly clusters bug reports and program details using TF-IDF representations (Hoang et al., 2019). NIOCAT combines execution data with test case names and error messages for failure grouping across development branches (Erman et al., 2015). Abbas et al. evaluated multiple encoding strategies including BERT alongside several clustering algorithms for failure log grouping (Abbas et al., 2023).

The novelty of our approach lies in systematic comparison of feature vectorization strategies tailored specifically to broadcast equipment testing, including component-weighted composite feature vectors inspired by multimodal approaches (Erman et al., 2015; Hoang et al., 2019). We apply these to HDBSCAN (Campello et al., 2015) and KMeans (Hartigan & Wong, 1979) clustering, then distribute the resulting clusters among engineers based on cosine distance to achieve equal workload distribution.

We address the following primary research question: *To what extent can clustering of composite feature vectors from failed test run log data identify coherent fault groups when testing RIEDEL MediorNet broadcasting equipment?* This decomposes into three subordinate questions: (RQ1) How does log text extraction mode affect fault group capture? (RQ2) Which combination of feature vectorization strategy and component weighting yields optimal geometric separation? (RQ3) Which algorithm—KMeans or HDBSCAN—proves more suitable for coherent clustering of semi-structured failed test run log data?

2 Methods

2.1 Research Design and Pipeline Architecture

We implement an empirical benchmarking approach evaluating a prototype software pipeline (Figure 1). The pipeline operates via REST API and executes five sequential stages: (1) data collection from failed test runs, (2) text-based feature preprocessing, (3) feature vectorization, (4) clustering, and (5) postprocessing to assign clusters to engineers such that workload balance is optimal while grouping similar clusters together.

2.2 Datasets

Two datasets support evaluation. The *Primary Dataset* (D_P) comprises 10,149 failed test runs spanning ≈ 89 weeks, with labels derived from issue tickets and tester database across 112 test campaigns. These labels represent operational annotations not originally intended for machine learning, thus subject to noise and incompleteness but providing sufficient scale for statistical analysis. The *Golden Sample* (D_{GS}) comprises 113 hand-curated failed test runs from October 3 to November 4, 2025, deliberately sampled across multiple campaigns to maximize label diversity. A domain expert assigned high-fidelity ground truth labels to D_{GS} for qualitative validation.

Exploratory analysis reveals substantial structural heterogeneity: test campaigns contain 90.6 ± 79.9 failed test runs with 20.6 ± 15.3 distinct fault groups per campaign. Single-entry labels (unique failures) comprise $40 \pm 19\%$ of labels per campaign. Label ubiquity analysis shows 56% of labels appearing in exactly one and 80% appearing in three or fewer test campaigns, precluding supervised classification due to insufficient stable training signals. Furthermore, identical error

Figure 1: Software pipeline architecture. Diamond shapes indicate configuration decisions. Blue: API interface. Yellow: data collection. Purple: text extraction (*FIRST*=first error/failure only vs. *FSWE*=all errors/failures) and domain specific preprocessing. Green: vectorization. Brown: clustering. Red: postprocessing and assignment.

texts frequently map to multiple distinct labels ($\approx 6\%$ of multi-label texts account for $\approx 25\%$ of all entries with all error and failure texts vs. $\approx 15\%$ of multi-label texts account for $\approx 51\%$ of all entries with first error/failure only) motivating composite feature vectors incorporating contextual information beyond raw log text.

2.3 Text Extraction and Preprocessing

We examine two log text extraction modes. *FIRST* retains only the initial error or failure annotation plus associated heading context, motivated by domain expertise suggesting first errors are often causally primary. *FSWE* (Failure, Stack trace, Warning, Error) aggregates all error, failure, and warning annotations, potentially capturing richer diagnostic context.

A five-stage preprocessing pipeline attenuates noise: (1) removal of domain-irrelevant tokens (timestamps, absolute paths), (2) replacement of variable-value tokens with typed placeholders to preserve semantic distinctions (IP addresses, path strings), (3) extraction and removal of per-line location identifiers, (4) retention of only exception messages from stack traces, and (5) deduplication of repeated log lines to prevent high-frequency entries from dominating representations as well as meeting BERT input token restrictions.

2.4 Feature Vectorization

We evaluate three feature vectorization strategies (FVS): `bert` utilizing the `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` sentence transformer for semantic similarity (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019), `tfidf` with sublinear TF scaling and log-IDF weighting for lexical overlap (Manning et al., 2008), and `combined` concatenating both representations for the log texts to assess complementarity.

Each failed test run is represented as a weighted composition of four feature vectors:

$$\vec{f} = V\vec{\alpha}, \quad V = [\vec{v}_1 \ \vec{v}_2 \ \vec{v}_3 \ \vec{v}_4], \quad \vec{\alpha} = (a, b, c, d)^T \quad (1)$$

where $\vec{v}_1 = \log \text{ text}$, $\vec{v}_2 = \text{test headings}$, $\vec{v}_3 = \text{test description}$, $\vec{v}_4 = \text{metadata (test topic, log category, failure report locations)}$. Each component is L2-normalized and scaled by $\sqrt{d_{ref}}$ before weighting, where d_{ref} is the maximum dimension among components, ensuring weights rather than vector dimensions determine relative influence.

We evaluate multiple weighting schemes: *baseline* (equal weights), expert-informed configurations emphasizing log text ($w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4, w_5, w_6$) with varying proportions of the remaining features, and ablation studies systematically removing one component (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) to assess individual contributions.

2.5 Clustering Algorithms

KMeans (Hartigan & Wong, 1979) establishes a baseline via `scikit-learn v1.7.1`. The number of clusters k is optimized and determined per test campaign using square-root scaling:

$$k_{\min} = \max(2, \lfloor 0.5\sqrt{n} \rfloor), \quad k_{\max} = \min(n - 1, \max(k_{\min} + 1, \lfloor 3.5\sqrt{n} \rfloor)) \quad (2)$$

with candidate set $\mathcal{K} = \{k_{\min} + si \mid i \in \mathbb{N}_0, k_{\min} + si < k_{\max}\}$ where $s = \max(1, \lfloor (k_{\max} - k_{\min})/10 \rfloor)$.

HDBSCAN (Campello et al., 2015) via `hdbscan v0.8.40` accommodates clusters of varying density without requiring predefined cluster counts. Hyperparameter grids span: `min_cluster_size` $\in [2, 3, 4, 5]$, `min_samples` $\in [1, 2, 3]$, `cluster_selection_epsilon` $\in [0.0, 0.1, 0.2]$, and `cluster_selection_method` $\in [\text{leaf}, \text{eom}]$ with precomputed cosine distance. Noise points are treated as single-member clusters rather than discarded. Excessive noise configurations are penalized during hyperparameter selection.

Both algorithms undergo per-test-campaign hyperparameter tuning to accommodate size and label distribution variance. For *KMeans*, optimal k is selected via majority vote across best-performing metrics or highest k if no consensus exists. For *HDBSCAN*, parameter combinations are selected via majority vote or lowest noise ratio when tied.

2.6 Evaluation Strategy

Feature vector quality is assessed via within-group (intra) and between-group (inter) cosine similarity of manually labeled fault groups. The Cluster Qualification Rate (CQR) captures the proportion of clusters satisfying $\text{intra} \geq 0.6$ and $\text{inter} \leq 0.3$, operationalizing geometric compactness and separability requirements derived empirically.

Clustering quality employs internal metrics (Silhouette Score (Rousseeuw, 1987), Calinski-Harabasz Index (Caliński & Harabasz, 1974), DBCV for HDBSCAN (Moulavi et al., 2014)) and external metrics (Adjusted Rand Index (Hubert & Arabie, 1985), V-Measure (Rosenberg & Hirschberg, 2007)). Statistical significance is assessed via pairwise Wilcoxon signed-rank tests (Wilcoxon, 1945) with Benjamini-Hochberg correction (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995), valid under positive regression dependence (Benjamini & Yekutieli, 2001), utilizing SciPy (Virtanen et al., 2020) implementation. Effect sizes are reported as rank-biserial correlation r with interpretation: trivial ($r < 0.1$), small ($r \geq 0.1$), medium ($r \geq 0.3$), large ($r \geq 0.5$), (*wilcox_essize: Wilcoxon Effect Size* 2023).

Golden sample validation presents cluster-to-expert-label mappings as confusion matrices with qualitative inspection of representative well- and poorly-clustered groups.

3 Results

3.1 Impact of Text Extraction Mode (RQ1)

Across all FVS configurations, intra-cluster similarity remains consistently high (0.74 ± 0.13 to 0.83 ± 0.10) while inter-cluster similarity stays low (0.06 ± 0.13 to 0.24 ± 0.14), indicating all combinations produce reasonably cohesive and separable clusters. `tfidf` achieves optimal separation at the cost of lower cohesion, while `bert` exhibits the opposite trade-off. The `combined` strategy balances both dimensions.

Statistical comparison via paired Wilcoxon tests reveals that extraction mode differences are negligible relative to FVS choice. For `bert`, both inter- and intra-group similarities differ significantly between *FSWE* and *FIRST* (both $p < 0.05$, $r_{\text{inter}} = -0.95$ favouring *FIRST* and $r_{\text{intra}} = 0.34$ favouring *FSWE*). For `tfidf` and `combined`, only inter-cluster similarity shows significance. Crucially, *FIRST* consistently produces better-separated clusters across all FVS (effect sizes $r = 0.71$ – 0.95 for inter-group similarity), while *FSWE* yields statistically significant higher within-group cohesion only under `bert`.

Figure 2 visualizes the intra-inter similarity relationship across test campaigns, confirming desired behaviour: inter-group similarities predominantly fall within $[0.0, 0.5]$ and intra-group similarities within $[0.5, 1.0]$. `tfidf` produces the most concentrated inter-group similarities invariant to extraction mode. `bert` shows greatest sensitivity to extraction mode, with *FSWE* producing denser clusters at moderate inter-similarity (≈ 0.2 – 0.35) while *FIRST* exhibits greater spread including high-similarity outliers.

RQ1 Answer: Text extraction mode exerts secondary influence relative to FVS choice. *FIRST* yields superior inter-group separation across all vectorization strategies while *FSWE* provides marginal cohesion improvements only with semantic embeddings. The null hypothesis of no systematic difference is partially rejected for between-group similarity but not replicated for within-group similarity.

3.2 Feature Vectorization Strategy and Component Weighting (RQ2)

We systematically evaluated weighting configurations including baseline (equal weights), expert-informed schemes emphasizing different components, and ablation studies removing individual features. Statistical comparison within each FVS and extraction mode stratum reveals weighting sensitivity varies substantially by FVS.

Figure 2: Intra- versus inter-label cosine similarity, mean per test campaign, colored by text extraction strategy and stratified by feature vectorization strategy. All three FVS types exhibit desired separation (inter-similarity predominantly below 0.5, intra-similarity above 0.5) under both extraction modes, though with varying degrees of concentration.

For **bert**, ablation configuration a_1 (removing metadata) consistently outperforms all alternatives under both extraction modes. Top-5 configurations achieve statistically significant improvements in cluster separation and proportion of well-separated groups relative to other weightings, though absolute differences in the top tier remain modest. Critically, removing metadata (\vec{v}_4 : test topic, log category, failure report locations) improves rather than degrades performance, contradicting initial expectations that metadata would provide disambiguating context.

For **tfidf**, removing log text entirely (a_4) yields optimal results, suggesting the repetitive nature of error messages reduces TF-IDF’s discriminative power due to high-frequency tokens shared across fault groups. Between-group similarity ranges only 0.06 ± 0.10 to 0.09 ± 0.10 , substantially lower than **bert** (0.20 ± 0.14 to 0.37 ± 0.12).

For **combined**, a_1 performs best under *FSWE* while w_1 (log text only) excels under *FIRST*. Top-ranked weightings systematically decrease within-group similarity to statistically significant degrees (effect sizes small to large) while improving separation.

RQ2 Answer: Optimal weighting is FVS-dependent rather than universal. Metadata components (\vec{v}_4) consistently fail to improve and often degrade performance. For BERT-based strategies, a_1 or w_1 (emphasizing log text without metadata) perform best. For TF-IDF, a_4 (excluding log text) proves superior. The null hypothesis of no weighting effect is rejected—weighting significantly affects intra- and inter-group similarities in most pairwise comparisons, though variance in effect sizes indicates susceptibility to fault type heterogeneity.

3.3 HDBSCAN versus KMeans Performance (RQ3)

Configuration-agnostic comparison averaging all FVS, extraction mode, and weighting combinations per TC reveals marginal KMeans advantage on external metrics: ARI (0.60 ± 0.22 vs. 0.57 ± 0.21 , $p < 0.05$) and V-Measure (0.83 ± 0.16 vs. 0.81 ± 0.17 , $p < 0.05$), though absolute differences remain small. Internal metrics diverge: Silhouette Score strongly favors HDBSCAN (0.73 ± 0.16 vs. 0.61 ± 0.23 , $p < 0.05$, 95.6% of test campaigns), while Calinski-Harabasz shows prohibitively high variance. ARI and V-Measure agree on 82.3% of per-test-campaign wins (Figure 3).

Configuration-level analysis ranking by combined ARI and V-Measure identifies top-5 combinations exclusively utilizing *FIRST* extraction, with w_1 (log text only) appearing three times. The overall best configuration is **bert-FIRST- w_1** for KMeans, while **bert-FIRST- w_4** ranks highest for HDBSCAN (4th overall).

Golden sample confusion matrices for the top-ranked configuration (Figure 4) show both

HDBSCAN vs K-Means — per test campaign (113) metric distributions across all tested configurations

Figure 3: Algorithm performance comparison across all test campaigns and configurations. External metrics show marginal differences, yet significant, while Silhouette favors HDBSCAN more strongly and Calinski-Harabasz was ignored due to being unstable.

algorithms struggle with identical difficult clusters—heterogeneous fault groups exhibiting low intra-group similarity (e.g., groups 36, 37) are split across multiple algorithmic clusters, while high inter-group similarity pairs (e.g., groups 3, 16) are merged. Notably, HDBSCAN produces less mixed clusters and identifies more single-member clusters (11 vs. 7 for KMeans), aligning better with domain expectations of isolated unique failures.

Internal-external metric alignment analysis reveals critical operational implications for hyperparameter selection in production deployment. For HDBSCAN, DBCV achieves 83% agreement with ARI in identifying optimal configurations, while default parameterization fails (21% agreement). For KMeans, the Silhouette Coefficient approximates ARI best (65% agreement) while the elbow method proves unreliable (23% agreement).

The distribution of ARI and V-Measure shows 69.8% of KMeans and 66.8% of HDBSCAN clusterings achieve $ARI > 0.5$, while 93.8% and 93.2% respectively achieve $V\text{-Measure} > 0.5$. Fifteen test campaigns consistently achieve $ARI < 0.5$ (intrinsic difficulty), 38 achieve $ARI > 0.5$ with low variance (≈ 0.10), leaving 60 configuration-sensitive campaigns.

RQ3 Answer: Both algorithms achieve comparable performance, with KMeans showing marginal external metric advantage ($ARI +0.03$, $V\text{-Measure} +0.02$) partly from aggressive hyperparameter optimization. However, HDBSCAN demonstrates superior practical suitability through: (1) density-based approach accommodating irregular failure spaces, (2) natural treatment of single-member clusters, (3) better internal-external metric alignment (DBCV 83% vs. Silhouette 65%) enabling reliable hyperparameter selection in production, and (4) geometrically more stable clusters. The null hypothesis is rejected, though effect sizes remain small for external metrics while large for internal metrics favoring HDBSCAN.

4 Discussion

4.1 Summary of Main Findings

This work demonstrates feasibility of unsupervised machine learning methods for pre-grouping failed test runs, achieving mean ARI of 0.57 ± 0.21 (HDBSCAN) and 0.60 ± 0.22 (KMeans) with V-Measure of 0.81 ± 0.17 and 0.83 ± 0.16 across 113 test campaigns. Key findings: (1) feature vectorization strategy dominates text extraction mode, with TF-IDF providing superior separation and BERT better cohesion, (2) metadata components unexpectedly degrade performance, and (3) HDBSCAN proves preferable for operational deployment despite KMeans' marginally higher

Figure 4: Confusion matrices comparing expert-labeled versus algorithm-generated clusters for golden sample under top-ranked configuration (*bert-FIRST-w_1*). Top: KMeans (cluster IDs 0–41). Bottom: HDBSCAN (cluster IDs -1–27, where -1 denotes noise points treated as single-member clusters). Cell values indicate failed test run counts assigned to each cluster. Color coding: yellow (complete agreement) to blue (expert cluster split). Red borders: expert cluster fragmented across multiple algorithmic clusters shared with other expert clusters. Golden Sample ARI 0.665 ± 0.088 , V-Measure 0.90 ± 0.05 .

external scores, due to better internal-external metric alignment and natural accommodation of single-member clusters.

The configuration-sensitivity of 60/113 test campaigns (53%) indicates optimization remains necessary for heterogeneous fault groups, while 15 consistently difficult campaigns (13%) reveal intrinsic limitations when fault symptoms vary substantially—an expected constraint of cosine similarity-based approaches.

4.2 Comparison with Related Work

Our results align with other research results. Abbas et al. (Abbas et al., 2023) report DBSCAN as best-performing with Silhouette Scores $\approx 0.87-0.92$ (larger models), concluding clustering serves as analysis aid rather than ground truth—resonating with our findings. Erman et al.’s NIOCAT (Erman et al., 2015) reports ARI 0.59-1.0 across scenarios, directly comparable to our range, suggesting susceptibility to fault structure is domain-inherent. We similarly achieve ARI=1.0 in well-structured test campaigns while struggling with heterogeneous cases.

4.3 Practical Implications and Limitations

The pipeline addresses redundant failure analysis through text-similarity-based pre-grouping. For the golden sample, test-system-based distribution would yield workload ratios of 7:13:26:45:22 failed test runs across five systems. HDBSCAN-based clustering with cosine distance achieves balanced assignment of 18/19 failed test runs per engineer (6 available) via cosine-distance-based cluster grouping (Figure 5), improving workload balance while minimizing context switches.

Figure 5: Cluster assignment dendrogram for golden sample. Bottom bars show cluster sizes colored by engineer assignment. Top dendrogram shows cluster similarity used for assignment grouping. Similar clusters are assigned together to minimize context switches while maintaining workload balance. Noise points are assigned afterwards in round robin fashion.

However, text-similarity-based approaches face fundamental limitations. When fault groups exhibit low intrinsic cohesion, symptoms vary despite shared root cause, similarity methods cannot reliably reconstruct expert boundaries. Golden sample analysis reveals: expert clusters 36

and 37 show low intra-group similarity ($\approx 0.4-0.5$) and are split with fragments mixed. Conversely, clusters 19-21 and 23 exhibit high mutual similarity and are merged into a thematic group, which experts confirm as related—demonstrating useful coarser-grained grouping even when fine-grained boundaries fail.

Given the one-year training period for new team members to discern failure root causes, automated pre-grouping provides substantial value despite imperfections, e.g., reducing workload and context switches.

4.4 Future Directions

Promising extensions include: domain-specific finetuning of embedding models for disambiguating similar log text in different fault contexts; re-evaluation of metadata integration through sophisticated feature engineering; and incorporation of source code features from software under test (Hoang et al., 2019) for finer-grained execution context. Operational improvements include test-system-aware noise grouping, failed test run content summarization via retrieval-augmented generation, persistence of cluster assignments across campaign re-runs, and ensemble approaches combining multiple FVS strategies.

4.5 Conclusion

This work establishes viability of unsupervised machine learning for automated pre-grouping of failed test runs, achieving sufficient agreement with expert-defined fault groups (mean ARI 0.57-0.60, V-Measure 0.81-0.83) for practical deployment. Systematic evaluation across 113 test campaigns reveals feature vectorization strategy as the primary performance determinant, with optimal configurations surprisingly excluding metadata. While KMeans achieves marginally superior external validation scores, HDBSCAN emerges as operationally preferable through better internal-external metric alignment and natural accommodation of single-member clusters.

Automated clustering accelerates manual analysis workflows that currently scale linearly with campaign size, providing particular value where domain expertise requires substantial training periods. Deployment at RIEDEL Communications represents a mature application of unsupervised machine learning to industrial testing workflows, with limitations in handling heterogeneous fault groups transparently communicated.

Author Contributions

Theresa Spiel conducted the research as part of her master’s thesis, including study conception, data collection, implementation of the clustering pipeline, experimental design, statistical analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The full master’s thesis is available from the library of the UAS Technikum Wien. Marius Fuehrer supervised the research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance throughout the project, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication. Stephan Grünfelder provided domain expertise from RIEDEL Communications, facilitated access to test data and infrastructure, contributed to problem formulation, and reviewed technical accuracy of the work. Beyond his technical contributions, he offered invaluable guidance throughout the thesis writing process and provided thorough, constructive feedback at every stage.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest. This research was conducted as part of a master’s thesis at University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien in collaboration with RIEDEL Communications Austria.

Data Availability

The datasets analyzed during this study are proprietary to RIEDEL Communications and contain confidential test data. Data are therefore not publicly available. The golden sample annotations and synthetic representative examples are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request and subject to appropriate non-disclosure agreements.

References

- Abbas, Muhammad, Hamayouni, Ali, Moghadam, Mahshid H., Saadatmand, Mehrdad & Strandberg, Per E. (2023). “Making Sense of Failure Logs in an Industrial DevOps Environment”. In: *ITNG 2023 20th International Conference on Information Technology-New Generations*. Ed. by Latifi, Shahram. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 217–226. ISBN: 978-3-031-28332-1.
- Benjamini, Yoav & Hochberg, Yosef (1995). “Controlling the False Discovery Rate: A Practical and Powerful Approach to Multiple Testing”. In: *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)* 57.1, pp. 289–300. ISSN: 00359246. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2346101> (visited on 04/03/2026).
- Benjamini, Yoav & Yekutieli, Daniel (Aug. 2001). “The control of the false discovery rate in multiple testing under dependency”. In: *The Annals of Statistics* 29.4, pp. 1165–1188. DOI: 10.1214/aos/1013699998.
- Caliński, T. & Harabasz, J. (1974). “A dendrite method for cluster analysis”. In: *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation* 3.1, pp. 1–27.
- Campello, Ricardo J. G. B., Moulavi, Davoud, Zimek, Arthur & Sander, Jörg (July 2015). “Hierarchical Density Estimates for Data Clustering, Visualization, and Outlier Detection”. In: *ACM Trans. Knowl. Discov. Data* 10.1. ISSN: 1556-4681. DOI: 10.1145/2733381. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2733381>.
- Egersdoerfer, Chris, Dai, Dong & Zhang, Di (Jan. 2023). “ClusterLog: Clustering Logs for Effective Log-based Anomaly Detection”. In: DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.2301.07846.
- Erman, Nicklas, Tufvesson, Vanja, Borg, Markus, Runeson, Per & Ardo, Anders (2015). “Navigating Information Overload Caused by Automated Testing - a Clustering Approach in Multi-Branch Development”. In: *2015 IEEE 8th International Conference on Software Testing, Verification and Validation (ICST)*, pp. 1–9. DOI: 10.1109/ICST.2015.7102596.
- Hartigan, J. A. & Wong, M. A. (1979). “Algorithm AS 136: A K-Means Clustering Algorithm”. In: *Applied Statistics* 28.1, pp. 100–108. ISSN: 00359254. DOI: 10.2307/2346830. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/2346830>.
- Hoang, Thong, Oentaryo, Richard J., Le, Tien-Duy B. & Lo, David (2019). “Network-Clustered Multi-Modal Bug Localization”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 45.10, pp. 1002–1023. DOI: 10.1109/TSE.2018.2810892.
- Hubert, Lawrence & Arabie, Phipps (1985). “Comparing partitions”. In: *Journal of Classification* 2.1, pp. 193–218. DOI: 10.1007/BF01908075.
- Lin, Qingwei, Zhang, Hongyu, Lou, Jian-Guang, Zhang, Yu & Chen, Xuewei (2016). “Log Clustering Based Problem Identification for Online Service Systems”. In: *2016 IEEE/ACM 38th International Conference on Software Engineering Companion (ICSE-C)*, pp. 102–111.
- Manning, Christopher D., Raghavan, Prabhakar & Schütze, Hinrich (2008). *Introduction to Information Retrieval*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. ISBN: 978-0-521-86571-5. URL: <http://nlp.stanford.edu/IR-book/information-retrieval-book.html>.
- Moulavi, Davoud, Jaskowiak, Pablo A., Campello, Ricardo J. G. B., Zimek, Arthur & Sander, Jörg (2014). “Density-Based Clustering Validation”. In: *Proceedings of the 2014 SIAM International Conference on Data Mining (SDM)*, pp. 839–847. DOI: 10.1137/1.9781611973440.96.

- eprint: <https://epubs.siam.org/doi/pdf/10.1137/1.9781611973440.96>. URL: <https://epubs.siam.org/doi/abs/10.1137/1.9781611973440.96>.
- Reimers, Nils & Gurevych, Iryna (Nov. 2019). “Sentence-BERT: Sentence Embeddings using Siamese BERT-Networks”. In: *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing and the 9th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (EMNLP-IJCNLP)*. Ed. by Inui, Kentaro, Jiang, Jing, Ng, Vincent & Wan, Xiaojun. Hong Kong, China: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 3982–3992. DOI: 10.18653/v1/D19-1410. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/D19-1410/>.
- RIEDEL Communications (2025). *Distributed Video Networks*. <https://www.riedel.net/en/products-solutions/distributed-video-networks>. Accessed: 2025-04-16.
- Rosenberg, Andrew & Hirschberg, Julia (June 2007). “V-Measure: A Conditional Entropy-Based External Cluster Evaluation Measure”. In: *Proceedings of the 2007 Joint Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing and Computational Natural Language Learning (EMNLP-CoNLL)*. Ed. by Eisner, Jason. Prague, Czech Republic: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 410–420. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/D07-1043/>.
- Rousseeuw, Peter J. (1987). “Silhouettes: A graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis”. In: *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics* 20, pp. 53–65. ISSN: 0377-0427. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-0427\(87\)90125-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-0427(87)90125-7). URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0377042787901257>.
- Virtanen, Pauli et al. (2020). “SciPy 1.0: Fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in Python”. In: *Nature Methods* 17, pp. 261–272. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2>.
- wilcox_effsize: Wilcoxon Effect Size* (2023). Online; accessed 11.04.2026. CRAN. URL: https://rdr.io/cran/rstatix/man/wilcox%5C_effsize.html.
- Wilcoxon, Frank (1945). “Individual Comparisons by Ranking Methods”. In: *Biometrics Bulletin* 1.6, pp. 80–83. ISSN: 00994987. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3001968> (visited on 04/03/2026).